

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348430774>

The Future of Applications For Clinical Decision Support Systems in Healthcare. Case Study: H2o2o PERSIST Project

Conference Paper · December 2020

CITATIONS

0

READS

621

5 authors, including:

Umut Arioiz

University of Maribor

29 PUBLICATIONS 33 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Baris Yildiz

Yasar University

7 PUBLICATIONS 46 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Ibrahim tolga Agim

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Kadir Üğüdücü

Emoda Software

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Patients-centered SurvivorShp care plan after Cancer treatments based on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence technologies [View project](#)

Master Thesis [View project](#)

The Future of Applications For Clinical Decision Support Systems in Healthcare. Case Study: H2020 PERSIST Project

Umut ARIÖZ¹, Barış YILDIZ², R. Alp KUT³, İbrahim Tolga AĞIM¹, Kadir ÜĞÜDÜCÜ¹

1 EMODA Yazılım ve Danışmanlık. San ve Tic Ltd Şti, IYTE Teknopark Urla İzmir,
umut@emodayazilim.com, info@emodayazilim.com, project@emodayazilim.com

2 Department of Software Engineering, Yaşar Üniversitesi Selçuk Yaşar Yerleşkesi, Bornova İzmir,
baris.yildiz@yasar.edu.tr

3 Semafor Teknoloji Yazılım Danışmanlık Ltd. Şti, Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İnciraltı Yerleşkesi, Balçova,
İzmir, alp.kut@semaforteknoloji.com

ABSTRACT

Clinical decision support systems (CDSS) are computer-based systems that leverage medical knowledge and patient-specific data to respond to a request for decision support by providing recommendations to improve the quality of the service provided to the patient. A complete and successful CDSS has a complex structure and includes various components from different scientific disciplines. Thus developers should take into account all faces of the CDSS while implementing the CDSS.

CDSS mainly consists of three components like a rule engine, an inference engine, and a mechanism to communicate. The rule engine directly depends on the data types which are based on a knowledge base, a non-knowledge base (artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms), or a hybrid of them. Although AI algorithms have become very popular in the healthcare sector as others, there are some restrictions and obstacles to use them directly in the health-related data and to gain the trustworthiness of the clinicians. One of the solutions to overcome these difficulties is to use the explainable AI (XAI) methods.

An effective CDSS needs to be fed by analysis of clinical or health-related data for constructing a knowledge base. Such data may include sensitive/personal information that needs to be anonymized and to be prevented from re-identification. This means that CDSS should comply with privacy/ethical concerns besides the technical requirements.

On the other hand, wearable technology which plays an important role in the functioning of the CDSS is becoming popular as a real-world data collector for heterogeneous and complex health-related data to support more accurate and personalized decisions for both patients and clinicians. Also, people using these smart devices in connection with CDSS via smart apps easily benefits from healthcare technologies like telemonitoring or telehealth. The importance of these kinds of technologies appeared more clearly nowadays. Because the COVID-19 situation showed us that people might have limited access to health services and have difficulties in all stages of treatment.

The PERSIST (Patient-centered SurvivorShip care plan after Cancer treatments based on Big Data and Artificial Intelligence technologies) project is an example approved H2020 project for all mentioned requirements for CDSS. PERSIST project aims at developing an open and interoperable ecosystem to improve the care of cancer survivors. PERSIST will advance the maturity level of existing algorithms that estimate the risk of re-identification in anonymized datasets. The role of CDSS in the PERSIST project is to provide patient-specific and actionable recommendations to health care providers for timely identification of symptoms and/or risks associated with the development of new medical conditions or impairments in the quality of life (QoL) of the patient.

Soon, CDSS will have a central role in the healthcare system with the help of algorithmic advances. This paper proposes possible directions of CDSS in healthcare while discussing the advances in the technology and the challenges for developing such systems by giving an example case study.

Keywords: Clinical decision support systems, knowledge base, wearable technology, explainable AI
